

WORKING WOMEN: REVIEWING THE MYTHS AND REALITIES

Bhawna Somani

¹Senior Research Fellow, Department of Commerce and Business Management, Ranchi University, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India.

ABSTRACT

Women comprise half the world's population but the persisting disproportion of their participation and involvement beyond domestic roles even in modern times is alarming. The previously published books, journals, reports, and articles in both online and offline modes have been used to gather a better understanding of workplace dynamics from women's point of view and evaluate the cause and effect of their deferred progression in leadership roles. The study discusses the nuances of women in the workplace and senior management positions; the various challenges they face every day in the professional domain, and sheds light upon the expectations and reality of the leadership roles by evaluating the pros and cons of more women having a seat at the top table. The outcomes reflect upon the serious under-representation of women in managerial roles caused by misplaced characterisation of the positions and identify means to close this gap in the foreseeable future.

KEYWORDS

Career Advancement; Challenges; Gender Discrimination; Leadership Roles; Women Leadership.

1. INTRODUCTION

Women's professional domain is forevermore an issue up for debate with their roles, competency, and performance subject to question. The traditional picture of domesticating women that deprived them of their professional picks remains a paradoxical one in contemporary times.

The world today is very different from decades ago, having witnessed an evolving proactive role of women in the income generation who have outgrown their passive roles and are now seeking as well as creating opportunities and privilege. There has been a serious shift in women from spending all or most of their time managing the household to confidently pursuing their ambitions moving past the odds of straddling between balancing the workplace and home (Shetty, 2018). With the changing notions of perceived gender roles worldwide, the drive for resurgence to employment and advancing up the ladder to leadership among women is on the rise.

Despite the upsurge, there exists a persistent gender gap in the labour workforce, as high as 57 points indicated by the World Bank Data and 52.1 points in India indicated by the International Labour Organisation as of 2022, with traces of very limited progress made by women in the professional arena over the past decade. The share of women advancing to leadership and managerial positions, though steadily increasing, is significantly low which raises an alarm worthy of investigation.

1.1. Need of the Study:

With a constant question hovering over their abilities, performance, and worthiness and facing passive discrimination at every step of progression, the need to understand women in the workplace is crucial to identify the cause and effect of their lagging pace of advancement. The misconception of leadership being a male bastion, and the predilection of women being born submissive are mythical.

Hence, the study is of utmost importance to comprehend what 'being a woman' in a workplace dominated by men means and enable organisations to make a perfect blend of the talent pool to realise their best potential moving over a patriarchal mindset.

1.2. Objectives of the Study:

- To study the transition of the role played by women in employment and leadership.
- To develop an in-depth understanding of the complexities associated.

1.3. Method of the Study:

The ease and simplification of the research process through technological advancement is a phenomenon to marvel at. Worldwide connectivity has widened reach and access to the existing body of knowledge, significantly raising the bar of quality in research. This study makes use of secondary data and consults several book chapters, journals, articles, and published research reports from both online and offline modes to develop a thorough understanding of the issue and draw inferences with a wider perspective.

2. Women in Employment and Leadership Roles: A Perspective

The world has and is still undergoing a gradual shift in women's perceived participation and involvement on multiple fronts – together at the house and in the workplace. Breaking the stereotype, women have shown immense potential to rise above the bar and excel in any field.

Although the major burden of domestic responsibility still falls on women as indicated by the (Global Gender Gap Report 2022, 2022) showing a serious disproportion in the share of time spent on unpaid to paid work between men and women, their spirit to prove themselves equally efficient in various fields of profession, worthy of advancing and capable of managing senior management positions persists.

More women partaking at work have sensitised the work environment adding the dimension of empathic considerations to human resource practices; organisations are underway valuing human resources as much as their other valuable assets. Organisations through diversity have been successful in laying a strong foundation of ethics and empathy and redefined the quality of work by integrating elements like compassion, and belongingness to blend with workplace disciplines.

Despite a steady increase in women's participation, the rise shows an uneven distribution across industries, concentrated in those where women are already adequately represented. However, with the rising confidence in women to pave their way themselves, the scenario is likely to change positively in the future.

What do women as leaders in an organisation bring to the table?

Leadership by definition or theory shows no favouritism for any gender, unlike the perpetual prejudice that widely characterises the position as masculine. Instead, for leadership to be effective, insist on the position being filled by a worthy candidate that qualifies the requirements and possesses attributes to put the formulated visions of the organisation into action effectively.

Women exhibit a natural talent for multitasking, efficient management, and making the best of available resources - all the qualities that make them highly resourceful as an employee and a suitable fit for managerial positions. Insightful leaders realise this potential too and have encouraged diversity for the role it plays in transforming ethos in a workplace and fostering the global scene of inclusive progress. Business leaders have urged organisations to adopt gender-neutral metrics in hiring and succession planning and have advocated for the belief that diversity in the workplace inspires diversity in thought-process too. More seats for women on the top table leverage the organisations into multiple perspectives and creative cognition in complex situations.

(Sadinovna, 2021) Several studies report that companies with more women at the leadership table and critical problem management roles perform better in comparison to those with fewer.

Women have added a new dimension to success with their differentiated leadership styles, painting a new picture of the desired qualities in an efficient leader that incorporates and integrates both masculine and feminine elements (Shetty, 2018). The leadership style adopted by women is more androgynous contrasting with the rigid reprimanding module by men. Their preference for a collaborative and more democratic approach is indeed unique and seemingly successful by far in dealing with modern workplace ramifications. (Eagly & Chin, 2010; Sadinovna, 2021; Vanderbroeck, 2010).

Several studies suggest that women are likely to be better mentors attributing to their understanding and problem-solving instincts. The shift of focus from achieving the pre-set goals subject to rigid protocols to emphasising on positive managerial strategies and harmony in the working environment is indeed a better-applicable fashion of getting the results for conspicuous corporations in modern times.

It is also of the general opinion that women are better suited to see the bigger picture and make cautious decisions as they are less likely to act rashly or fall for the traps of quick returns, unlike men.

Regardless of the said advantages, women still somehow struggle for positive performance support and are expected to be content with limited advancement opportunities at work. Although the trend in the women's leadership dashboard shows an increase according to (Global Gender Gap Report 2022, 2022) from 33.3% in 2016 to 36.9% in 2022, the growth does not seem very encouraging by the expected standards. According to *Women in Managerial and Leadership Positions in the G20 Data Availability and Preliminary Findings*, the SDG's expected target of 50% representation of women in managerial positions stands below 30 per cent according to the recent suggestive report.

Hence, women's under-representation in senior management positions and status derogatory to 'token appointments' or 'risky promotions' in the twenty-first century raises a global concern.

3. Stumbling Blocks for Women

The old tradition of expecting women to submit that stems from patriarchal society dumps the responsibilities of caretaking for elders, children, and household chores majorly on women. Juggling between unrealistic societal expectations and their ambitions, maintaining a work-life balance by women, married or not is extremely difficult.

In addition to the family and societal setting barriers, the pressure to prove themselves worthy of their position in work along with fighting the persistent bias is unreal. Their differentiated personal priorities such as inevitable career breaks, reluctance to fill roles that require relocating or travel, and the demand for a fair share of their time at home to fulfil duties towards children and marriage amidst professional targets are some constant battles women face in their everyday lives.

Hence, the aspirations overshadowed by responsibilities, often misinterpreted as lacking the drive to succeed hold back women from advancing at the same pace as men in their careers.

3.1. Problems in the workplace:

Several studies (Jayam, n.d.; Sharma & Sehrawat, 2014; Sharma & Kaur, 2019; Chugh & Sahgal, 2007) indicate inhospitable culture contaminated by stereotypes and the failure of organisations to stop the gender-biased mechanisms still in practice as the key restraining factors for women causing their sojourn in the workplace. The studies provide evidence of women admitting to unfair treatment in the face of being assigned less important tasks, limited variation in experience, and deliberate attempts to sabotage performance with unattainable targets to stall.

In addition to already overshadowed existence in the male-dominated environment, normalised undervalued contributions, pay-scale differences, and often being caught in competency clusters are some unfortunate constants for women to face in the workplace. Despite strict measures and policies installed against the practice, sexual harassment persisting at different levels is regrettable.

Women have priorities and goals different from men even professionally. They strive for an inclusive, healthy, and interactive environment overpower unlike men, the meaning of which is easily misplaced as lacking determination and desire to lead.

3.2.Challenges in Leadership:

Besides the 'token appointments' of women in leadership positions mandated by various government-passed bills, very few women make it to the top. Owing to serious under-representation on the leadership table, male dominance in work culture, and a lack of an organised female network, women are less likely to move vertically up the corporate ladder.

(Ibarra, Carter, & Silva, 2010) The survey reports efficient mentorship for both men and women, yet women lack the sponsorship as enthusiastically as men, as a result, fail to progress. Encouraged, supported, and mentored but women lack endorsement enough to uplift them to the managerial chair.

The double standards hoping women to embody feminine compassion and tenderness by nature yet remain disguised behind the veil of masculine assertions and dominance as a leader should is a peak of hypocrisy that bind women by the double-blind dilemma. (Eagly & Chin, 2010; Vanderbroeck, 2010) as a leader.

Moreover, the chances for women leaders to face resistance are usually high as men refuse to take orders from a woman under the vainglory. The expectation of not being deterred by derogatory prepossessions and demonstrating the uncharacteristically exceptional ability of multi-tasking add to their psychological pressure in the position of charge.

3.3.The Repercussion of Complexities:

Beating all the odds, women still have managed to forge their own path to success anyway. The tales of their rise and success can be seen across industries with organisations promoting and celebrating the spirit of women's empowerment, cheering for their women workforce. However, every struggle to turn into success requires paying price or sacrifices. Women are no different from this principle. Discussed below are some repercussions on women:

- According to (Global Gender Gap Report 2022, 2022) data by Hologic reporting a higher level of stress in women than in men, women's emotional and mental well-being is an area for concern.
- Breaking self-confidence, rising insecurities, and self-deprecating tendencies among women.
- Prolonged lack of performance support and unrecognised value results in under-performance, inefficiency, and high turnover.
- Untreated prejudice and prominent gender-biased mechanisms poison the work culture and inspire conflicts and discord.
- Deferred opportunity for career advancement discourages the participation of women in the workforce and reduces organisations to underutilise human resources.
- Damages the public image and financials to the organisation facing legal charges and high-cost settlement of claims against unfair practices.

4. Workaround Recommendations:

Women make part of the unrealised talent pool that needs harnessing to achieve heights. Now that women are keen to face stronger headwinds than men in work, seeking their due recognition and chasing their ambition with self-assurance, dealing with the associated complexities requires a different approach.

4.1.Organisational Measures:

Organisations are required to take active measures in devising upliftment programs and flexible policies for women with due consideration to their personal and professional barriers that help them reach their standards of excellence. The responsibility of eradicating gender stereotypes from the work culture by sensitising men to effective collaboration, promoting team spirit, and developing advancement metrics free from gender biases hugely falls on the organisations.

Vigorous policy against sexual harassment, unethical pay differentiations, and undue influence of favouritism along with strong retention strategies that aim to reduce attrition needs to be put in motion to ensure fair practices and the development of a culture that cherishes efficiency irrespective of demographic differences. This includes developing online and offline platforms for women to network and share their thoughts to share a common sense of security and belongingness and seek bits of advice for advancement from colleagues.

Endorsing the success stories of women leaders and seeking image consultations to improve the portrait of the role played by them could go a long way in changing the prejudiced mindset of the public in general (Jayam, n.d.).

4.2. Personal Upliftment:

Relying upon organisations to seek relief for all the problems is unfair as empowerment begins from within. Women need to outgrow their insecurities and aggressively chase their ambitions, unperturbed by hypocritical expectations laid out by society.

Closely studying the dynamics of their workplace, setting their priorities straight, defining their professional goals clearly, and beginning actively networking to search for answers to their hurdles are some recommended steps. Voicing opinions and demanding their rights are the pointers to breaking through the pressure of dominance and suppression.

Open communication with family about duties and expectations, time management, and work-life balance go a long way in protecting both personal and professional life from shambles as a whole.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The fast-changing dynamics of the world are supportive of the progression and inclusion of women as compared to history. Women have reached the top and proved gender to be no bar for competency or leadership. This gives a right to expect a positive turnaround, breaking the traditional picture of patriarchy and seeing women rising beyond prejudice across the globe in the foreseeable future; strengthening the foundation of modern society by setting the right examples for future generations. Though the study covers a 360-degree view of understanding women in a workplace, the issue remains worthy to be extended further in research seeking answers on multiple aspects such as intellectual, emotional, volition, and psychological quotients in a workplace, to infer an in-depth understanding of the same, draw comparisons and propose problem-solving recommendations under circumstances. Encouraging women to pursue their professional picks and contribute potential in leadership positions is creating a far more durable asset for an economy with a real sense of celebrating the spirit of women's empowerment.

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